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A PowerPoint presentation of the project**

**Vaccine for Prevention and Treatment of
Trypanosoma cruzi Infection
(CRUZIVAX)**

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Version 1**

Main Author(s) (usually WP leader(s)):

First name: Carlos

Family Name: Guzmán

Institution: HZI

Country: Germany

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Author(s)	Kai Schulze and Carlos Guzmán
Project coordinator	Prof. Carlos A. Guzmán, HZI, Germany
EC Project Officer	Dr. Maria Klimathianaki

Table of Contents

1. INTRODUCTION	3
2. RESULTS.....	4

1. Introduction

The project presentation will provide the background information to the project and its goals. This can be used by the partners for presenting the project. The presentation will be updated regularly.

2. Results

CRUZIVAX Project – Horizon2020

Preclinical and clinical validation of a vaccine against Chagas disease

Chagas disease

Trypanosoma cruzi

- Classical transmission
- Organ transplantation
- Transfusion
- Perinatal

Schematic representation of the life cycle of the flagellate protozoan *Trypanosoma cruzi*
Expert Reviews in Molecular Medicine ©2002 Cambridge University Press

Chagas disease... a global problem

21 endemic and 19 non-endemic countries

World Health Organization. (2013)
www.who.int/iris/handle/10665/77950

Chagas disease

Source: www.cdc.gov/tbdc

- ❑ ~10 million infected individuals who will progress to chronicity
- ❑ 30-40% chronically infected develop **life-threatening** clinical forms
- ❑ Disability adjusted life-year (DALYs): **252,000/year**
- ❑ Huge financial burden (annual costs > **EUR 6 billion**)
- ❑ Drugs only active in **early infection**, **lengthy** and **highly toxic**
- ❑ **No vaccine** available

CRUZIVAX Project

Develop an intranasal needle-free vaccine against *T. cruzi* infection

CRUZIVAX™

- ❑ Chimeric trivalent synthetic antigen (Traspain)
- ❑ HZI's new adjuvant c-di-AMP

CRUZIVAX™ proof-of-concept

Sanchez Alberti *et al.* (2017) *npj Vaccines*

Expertise of the partners

Partner / acronym / type org	Expertise
1 Helmholtz-Zentrum für Infektionsforschung GmbH (HZI) Research Organisation	Immunology, murine preclinical validation models , immune monitoring in preclinical models and humans, vaccinology, adjuvants , project management, communication, dissemination, exploitation
2 Universidad de Buenos Aires (UBA) University	Immunology, vaccinology, parasitology, Chagas disease R&D , communication, dissemination, exploitation
3 Universidade Nova de Lisboa (UNL-IHMT) University	Parasitology, immunology, dog infection models , communication, dissemination, exploitation
4 Atomic Energy Commission (CEA-IDMIT) Research organisation	Vaccines, immunology, infectious diseases, non-human primate models , communication, dissemination, exploitation
5 Instituto de Biología Experimental e Tecnológica (IBET) SME	Discovery research, preclinical development, prophylactic/therapeutic and human/veterinary vaccines , project management, communication, dissemination, exploitation
6 GenIBET Biopharmaceuticals SA (GenIbet) SME	Scale-up, technology transfer and GMP manufacturing , communication, dissemination, exploitation
7 ASA-Spezialenzyme GmbH (ASA) SME	Scale-up, technology transfer and GMP manufacturing , enzyme technology, gene technology, communication, dissemination, exploitation
8 Aurigon Toxicological Research Center Ltd (ATRC) SME	GLP-certified testing facility, conduct of immunization studies, conduct of GLP-compliant toxicity studies in rodent and non-rodent species , bioanalytical method development and validation, communication, dissemination, exploitation
9 University of Antwerp (CEV) University	Vaccinology, conduct of clinical trials (phase 1-4) , immunology, communication, dissemination, exploitation
10 Barcelona Institute for Global Health (ISGlobal) Research organisation	Health economics of infectious diseases in low- and middle- income countries , communication, dissemination, exploitation
11 Vakzine Projekt Management GmbH (VPM) SME	Regulatory consulting , vaccine development from bench to bedside including technology transfer to GMP manufacturing, non-clinical and clinical development, clinical trial sponsorship phase 1-3 , clinical project management , communication, dissemination, exploitation

cruzivax

CRUZIVAX Project

C.A. Guzmán

M. Carrondo

C.A. Guzmán

G. Santos-Gomes

I. Novák

L. Grode

E. Sicuri

Development of vaccine components

GLP & GMP production of the vaccine components

Preclinical validation of the vaccine in different animal models

Toxicology

Preparation and implementation of a clinical phase I trial

Health economics studies and demand assessment

E. Malchiodi

A. Cordes

E. Malchiodi

R. Le Grand

C.A. Guzmán

P. Van Damme

Project objectives

- ❑ **preclinical identification** of the best vaccine formulation and vaccination strategy in prophylactic and therapeutic settings **in mice**
- ❑ assess the **immunogenicity** and the prophylactic and therapeutic **efficacy** of the best vaccine formulation and vaccination strategy **in dogs and non-human primates (NHP)**
- ❑ establish the production processes of good laboratory practice (**GLP**) and good manufacturing practice (**GMP**) grade antigen and adjuvant
- ❑ provide **non-toxicology data and safety assessment** of the vaccine candidate
- ❑ assess the safety and immunogenicity of the vaccine candidate through a **clinical phase 1 study** in healthy volunteers
- ❑ determine the potential demand and supply for the Traspain vaccine, as well as critical field implementation parameters by performing a flanking **health economic analysis**

CRUZIVAX – Project Structure

CRUZIVAX – Timing of WPs

WP	Title	Year 1			Year 2			Year 3			Year 4			Year 5		
		Q1	Q2	Q3												
1	Immunogenicity and efficacy of Traspain+CDA in mice															
2	Therapeutic efficacy of Traspain+CDA in infected mice															
3	Immunogenicity and efficacy of Traspain+CDA in dogs															
4	Therapeutic efficacy of Traspain+CDA in infected dogs															
5	Immunogenicity and efficacy of Traspain+CDA in NHP															
6	Therapeutic efficacy of the Traspain+CDA in infected NHP															
7	Production of GLP-grade Traspain and CDA															
8	Production of GMP-grade Traspain and CDA															
9	Formulation, filling and stability of Traspain and CDA															
10	Non-clinical safety assessment studies of Traspain+CDA															
11	Phase I clinical trial regulatory and infrastructure setup															
12	Phase I clinical trial preparation, application and management															
13	Phase I clinical trial implementation															
14	Demand side: Quality of life and demand for Traspain+CDA															
15	Life-long use of resources and associated costs for Chagas disease															
16	Management, communication, dissemination and exploitation 1															
17	Management, communication, dissemination and exploitation 2															
18	Management, communication, dissemination and exploitation 3															
19	Ethics requirements															

CRUZIVAX – Timing of WPs

WP	Title	Year 1			Year 2			Year 3			Year 4			Year 5		
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q1	Q2	Q3
1	Immunogenicity and efficacy of Traspain-CDA in mice				M1.1*	M1.2										
	Task 1.1: Production of research grade recombinant Traspain															
	Task 1.2: Harmonization of the immune response monitoring															
	Task 1.3: Safety and Tolerability of Traspain and Traspain-CDA				D1.1											
	Task 1.4: Traspain-CDA immunogenicity in young female mice															
	Task 1.5: Traspain-CDA immunogenicity in young male mice						D1.2									
	Task 1.6: Validation of the best vaccination strategy in adult mice															
	Task 1.7: Traspain-CDA vaccine efficacy against <i>T. cruzi</i>									D1.3						
	Task 1.8: Traspain-CDA capacity to prevent <i>T. cruzi</i> persistence															
2	Therapeutic efficacy of Traspain-CDA in infected mice							M2.1*	M2.2							
	Task 2.1: Mice infection and treatment protocols															
	Task 2.2: Treatment efficacy analysis										D1.1					
	Task 2.3: Antigen and pathogen-specific immune response											D1.2				
3	Immunogenicity and efficacy of Traspain-CDA in dogs							M3.1	M3.2		M3.3					
	Task 3.1: Accommodation of Beagle dogs															
	Task 3.2: Dog immunization						D3.1									
	Task 3.3: Immunogenicity of Traspain-CDA in dogs									D3.1						
	Task 3.4: <i>T. cruzi</i> inoculum for challenge studies															
	Task 3.5: Vaccine efficacy against <i>T. cruzi</i> challenge in dogs											D3.3				
4	Therapeutic efficacy of Traspain-CDA in infected dogs										M4.1	M4.2				
	Task 4.1: Treatment of <i>T. cruzi</i> chronic infected dogs															
	Task 4.2: Vaccine therapeutic efficacy in <i>T. cruzi</i> infected dogs											D4.1	D4.3			
	Task 4.3: Traspain-CDA responses in chronically infected dogs														D4.1	

CRUZIVAX – Timing of WPs

WP	Title	Year 1			Year 2			Year 3			Year 4			Year 5		
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q1	Q2	Q3
5	Immunogenicity and efficacy of Traspain-CDA in NHP							M5.1/3	M5.4		M5.5	M5.6				
	Task 5.1: Establishing the <i>T. cruzi</i> infection model in macaques						D5.1									
	Task 5.2: Assess vaccine immunogenicity and safety in NHP						D5.2/D5.3									
	Task 5.3: Assess vaccine efficacy in NHP									D5.4/D5.5						
6	Therapeutic efficacy of the Traspain-CDA in infected NHP													M6.1	M6.2	M6.3
	Task 6.1: Vaccine immunogenicity in <i>T. cruzi</i> infected NHP									D6.1					D6.2	
	Task 6.2: Evaluate vaccine efficacy in <i>T. cruzi</i> infected NHP														D6.3	D6.4
7	Production of GLP-grade Traspain and CDA							M7.1								
	Task 7.1: Establishment of supporting analytical techniques						D7.1									
	Task 7.2: Establishment of Master Cell Bank under cGMP conditions						D7.1									
	Task 7.3: Traspain for preclinical studies						D7.3									
	Task 7.4: Traspain production for GLP-toxicology						D7.4									
	Task 7.5: CDA for preclinical and GLP-toxicology studies															
8	Production of GMP-grade Traspain and CDA										M8.1	M8.2*		M8.3		
	Task 8.1: Traspain cGMP production for phase 1															
	Task 8.2: CDA cGMP production for phase 1												D8.1			
	Task 8.3: Preparation of all documents															
9	Formulation, filling and stability of Traspain and CDA													M9.1*	M9.2	
	Task 9.1: Biological activity and stability of CDA and Traspain						D9.1									
	Task 9.2: Formulation, filling and quality control															
	Task 9.3: Stability testing														D9.2	D9.3*
10	Non-clinical safety assessment studies of Traspain-CDA															
	Task 10.1: GLP-toxicity studies						M10.1								M10.2	
																D10.1

CRUZIVAX – Timing of WPs

WP	Title	Year 1			Year 2			Year 3			Year 4			Year 5		
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3
11	Phase 1 clinical trial regulatory and infrastructure setup	*M11.1			*M11.2											
	Task 11.1: First scientific advice meeting with Belgian regulators															
	Task 11.2: Second scientific advice meeting															
	Task 11.3: Qualification audits to set-up infrastructure															
12	Phase 1 clinical trial preparation, application and management															
	Task 12.1: Trial management, logistics and engagement of required subcontractors															D12.4*
	Task 12.2: CTA to ethics committee and national authority															
	Task 12.3: Clinical trial organisation															
13	Phase 1 clinical trial implementation															
	Task 13.1: Phase 1 clinical trial of the vaccine candidate															
	Task 13.2: Exploratory endpoints vaccine immunogenicity															D13.2/D13.3/D13.4*
	Task 13.3: Comparison of the efficacy and immunogenicity of the various species															D13.5/D13.6*
14	Demand side: Quality of life and demand for Traspain-CDA	*M14.1			*M14.2											
	Task 14.1: Defining attributes and modalities for DCE															
	Task 14.2: Preparation of DCEs following best practices															
	Task 14.3: REDCap/ODK for DCEs to policy makers & patients															
	Task 14.4: DCEs piloting, data collection and monitoring															
	Task 14.5: Data management, cleaning and analysis															
	Task 14.6: Obtain EQ-SQ from Eurocol															
	Task 14.7: Incorporate the EQ-SQ questionnaire into platform															
	Task 14.8: Piloting, Data collection, data monitoring															
	Task 14.9: Data analysis															

CRUZIVAX – Timing of WPs

WP	Title	Year 1			Year 2			Year 3			Year 4			Year 5		
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3
15	Life-long use of resources and associated costs for Chagas disease															
	Task 15.1: Data mining															
	Task 15.2: Estimate of life-long costs for Chagas disease															
16	Management, communication, dissemination and exploitation 1	*M16.1														
	Task 16.1: Project management and coordination															
	Task 16.2: Communication, dissemination and exploitation															
17	Management, communication, dissemination and exploitation 2															
	Task 17.1: Project management and coordination															
	Task 17.2: Communication, dissemination and exploitation															
18	Management, communication, dissemination and exploitation 3															
	Task 18.1: Project management and coordination															
	Task 18.2: Communication, dissemination and exploitation															
19	Ethics requirements															

CRUZIVAX – First in human study

Clinical trial scheme

CRUZIVAX – Clinical Trial

First-in-human subject and evaluator blinded, placebo-controlled

- ❑ **Safety, reactogenicity, tolerability and immunogenicity** of two different intranasal dose levels of a Traspain-based vaccine (CRUZIVAX™) with a cyclic-di-AMP (CDA) adjuvant in healthy subjects aged 18-50 years
- ❑ **60 subjects** will be enrolled into the study
- ❑ Subjects will receive **3 doses at days 0, 21 and 42**
- ❑ CRUZIVAX™ / CDA will be investigated at three dose levels: low/low, high/low and high/high
- ❑ Each of the 4 arms (including placebo) will include 15 subjects
- ❑ Subjects will be followed-up until **120 days** post-prime vaccination

CRUZIVAX – Objectives of the Clinical Trial

Primary objectives:

- ❑ Assess unsolicited and solicited **serious adverse events (SAEs)** of CRUZIVAX™ / CDA from Day 1 to the end of the trial
- ❑ Assess unsolicited and solicited **reactogenicity** (local and systemic) events of CRUZIVAX™ / CDA from Day 1 to Day 7 post vaccination
- ❑ Assess unsolicited and solicited **severe adverse events (AEs)** of CRUZIVAX™ / CDA from Day 1 to Day 7 post vaccination

Secondary objectives:

- ❑ Assess **immunogenicity** of CRUZIVAX™ / CDA: measurement of antibody response by ELISA (antigen-specific IgG titre and analyses for seroconversion), collected from baseline until Day 120 post-prime

CRUZIVAX – Management Structure

CRUZIVAX – Executive Board

Proposed Executive Board members	Partner	Gender
C. A. Guzmán - Coordinator (Chair); (WP1&16-18 leader)	P1-HZI	M
E. Malchiodi - Deputy Coordinator (WP2 leader)	P2-UBA	M
G. Santos-Gomes (WP3&4 leader)	P3-UNL-IHMT	F
R. Le Grand (WP5&6 leader)	P4-CEA-IDMIT	M
M. Carrondo (WP7 leader)	P5-iBET	M
A. Cordes (WP8&9 leader)	P7-ASA	M
I. Novak (WP10 leader)	P8-ATRC	M
L. Grode (WP11 leader)	P11-VPM	M
P. Van Damme (WP12&13 leader)	P9-CEV	M
E. Sicuri (WP14&15 leader)	P10-ISGlobal	F
Project Manager B. Prochnow (nv*)	P1-HZI	M

CRUZIVAX – WP Leaders

WP	Leader (gender)	Partner	Country
1	C. A. Guzmán (M)	P1-HZI	Germany
2	E. Malchiodi (M)	P2-UBA	Argentina
3 & 4	G. Santos-Gomes (F)	P3-UNL-IHMT	Portugal
5 & 6	R. Le Grand (M)	P4-CEA-IDMIT	France
7	M. Carrondo (M)	P5-iBET	Portugal
8 & 9	A. Cordes (M)	P7-ASA	Germany
10	I. Novak (M)	P8-ATRC	Hungary
11	L. Grode (M)	P11-VPM	Germany
12 & 13	P. Van Damme (M)	P9-CEV	Belgium
14 & 15	E. Sicuri (F)	P10-ISGlobal	Spain
16-18	C. A. Guzmán (M)	P1-HZI	Germany

CRUZIVAX – Exploitation

- ❑ **Implementation of proactive IP rights strategy** for protection and targeted exploitation of results
- ❑ Installation of an **Innovation Committee** to maximize impact and optimal exploitation of data
- ❑ Close interaction with the relevant regulatory authorities aiming at a **rapid market authorization** of the vaccine after a successful phase I trial
- ❑ **Providing research data** to the scientific community by **open access** publications

CRUZIVAX – Dissemination

- ❑ Implementation of a **strategic plan to integrate science and technology in the society**
- ❑ Establishment of a project **corporate identity image** for CRUZIVAX
- ❑ Establishment and further development of an **external website** (www.cruzivax.eu)
- ❑ Development and implementation of a **communication plan**
- ❑ Regular project internal **information exchange** for knowledge, data and experience sharing
- ❑ Workshop for young scientists leading to interdisciplinary understanding and **knowledge transfer**

Expected outcome

- ❑ First-in-human studies of CRUZIVAX™ as prophylactic vaccine candidate against Chagas disease
- ❑ Evaluation of CRUZIVAX™ efficacy as therapeutic vaccine alone and in combination with anti-parasitic drugs in 3 animal species
- ❑ Evaluation of the efficacy of CRUZIVAX™ as prophylactic veterinary vaccine in relevant animal species
- ❑ Identification of potential biomarkers and/or correlates of protection for future studies
- ❑ Health economic analysis in endemic (under-resourced) and non-endemic areas

Trypanosomiasis, American (Chagas disease) (*Trypanosoma cruzi*)

<https://phil.cdc.gov/>

CRUZIVAX Project – Horizon2020

Preclinical and clinical validation of a
vaccine against Chagas disease

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 815418.